

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	RADPatch - Radiation Resilience Evaluation of SpacePatch: A System-Level Proton Beam Study
Project TA identifier	TA13-447
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE
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Date(s) of the experiment	30.09.2025 – 01.10.2025
Facility	HollandPTC
Amount of access granted	8h

Objectives of the experiments

Human space exploration beyond Low Earth Orbit (LEO) demands continuous, reliable health monitoring systems that can operate under harsh radiation environments. Conventional commercial wearable devices, while adequate for ISS missions, are not designed to withstand the increased radiation levels encountered during long-duration lunar and Martian missions. In response to this challenge, the Smart Sensors Group at TUHH has developed SpacePatch, an autonomous, wearable sensor platform based on a “careful COTS for space” design philosophy. Key components of SpacePatch have already demonstrated strong Total Ionizing Dose (TID) tolerance exceeding 70 krad during electron irradiation and in-orbit operation aboard the ISS. The proposed RADPatch project aims to extend this qualification by performing the first system-level proton irradiation test of the complete SpacePatch device. Proton irradiation is selected because protons dominate the space radiation environment beyond LEO and are a primary cause of Single Event Effects (SEEs), including Single Event Upsets (SEUs) and potentially destructive events such as latch-ups. Testing across multiple proton energies (50–200 MeV) allows realistic emulation of space-relevant conditions and enables identification of radiation-sensitive hotspots at the system level. SpacePatch itself serves as the primary test vehicle, as it integrates all critical subsystems required for astronaut health monitoring, including a MEMS IMU, ultra-low-power FPGA, BLE SoC, and flash memory. This high level of integration makes it an ideal platform for evaluating cross-component interactions and failure propagation under radiation. In parallel, the experiment will assess a novel In-System Failure Detection (ISFD) [1] mechanism developed for resource-constrained FPGAs, providing insight into energy-efficient fault detection as an alternative to conventional scrubbing approaches. Overall, RADPatch will deliver critical knowledge for designing resilient, radiation-tolerant wearable systems, advancing astronaut health monitoring technologies for future deep-space missions.

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Experiment test report

Figure-01: Experiment Setup of the Unit under Irradiation.

This report summarizes preliminary results from the RADPatch proton irradiation experiment, conducted to evaluate proton-induced Single Event Effects (SEEs) in the SpacePatch wearable sensor system and to assess the effectiveness of an In-System Failure Detection (ISFD) mechanism [1] implemented on an ultra-low-power FPGA. The experiment represents the first system-level proton irradiation of SpacePatch under space-relevant conditions.

A total of eight Devices Under Test (DUTs) were prepared for the experiment:

- Four fully assembled SpacePatch wearable sensor systems
- Four standalone FPGAs implementing the ISFD mechanism

Due to irradiation time constraints, three SpacePatch units and three FPGA DUTs were exposed to the proton beam. The remaining devices were retained as non-irradiated reference samples.

Each SpacePatch integrates a MEMS IMU, ultra-low-power FPGA, BLE SoC, and external flash memory. Available device identification data (manufacturer, part number) was recorded prior to testing; wafer-level information was not available for all components.

The experiment was conducted at HollandPTC. Proton irradiation was selected due to its relevance for inducing SEEs in deep-space environments.

- Particle: Protons
- Energies: 50, 70, 120, and 200 MeV
- Beam size: 4 cm × 4 cm

All irradiated DUTs were powered and operating during exposure. Voltage, current, temperature, and system status were continuously monitored.

Initial Results and Observations:

This section summarizes the preliminary observations obtained during the proton irradiation campaign. Results are divided into two parts:

(i) system-level behavior of the SpacePatch wearable platform and

(ii) validation of the In-System -Failure-Detection (ISFD) mechanism implemented on the FPGA.

1. SpacePatch System-Level Evaluation:

Figure 2 presents the proton flux, cumulative fluence, and absorbed dose as a function of time for a representative SpacePatch unit (DUT-05). Red dotted vertical markers indicate the time instants at which SEUs were observed. DUT-05 was irradiated in five runs, with four runs at 120 MeV followed by one run at 200 MeV.

Figure 2: Radiation Exposure of SpacePatch (DUT-05)

Before each irradiation run, the system was power-cycled to eliminate residual effects. No continuous configuration readback or scrubbing was performed during exposure in order to preserve normal system operation. All subsystems remained powered and operational throughout irradiation. Post-irradiation analysis included full firmware verification of the BLE SoC, readout of all available status registers, and a complete dump of the external flash memory. The BLE SoC was identified as the most radiation-sensitive component, with repeated UART communication failures observed after irradiation. These failures are currently under investigation and are suspected to originate from SEUs in internal control or status registers, motivating further research on implementing rad-tolerant mechanisms on the SoC.

All observed upsets were non-destructive. The entire device was restored after a simple power cycle. No latch-up events, permanent functional failures, or abnormal current increases were detected.

2. ISFD Validation:

A total of three ultra-low-power (ULP) FPGA devices were irradiated to evaluate the In-System Failure Detection (ISFD) mechanism [1] under proton exposure. Figure 3 shows the time-resolved proton flux, cumulative fluence, and absorbed dose for a representative FPGA unit (DUT-06). DUT-06 was irradiated over six runs to reach a cumulative fluence of approximately 4.5×10^{11} p/cm², with the first five runs conducted at 120 MeV and the final run at 200 MeV.

Figure 3: Radiation Exposure of iCE40 ULP FPGAs (DUT-06)

Prior to each irradiation run, the system was power-cycled to ensure a well-defined initial state. During irradiation, FPGA IP cores were periodically tested every 30 seconds using the ISFD technique. Red dotted vertical markers indicate the first detection of SEUs during each irradiation run, after which an increased number of IP core failures was observed.

These results constitute the first successful experimental validation of the ISFD mechanism under proton irradiation, demonstrating its capability to detect radiation-induced faults in ULP FPGAs without continuous configuration readback. Furthermore, this study serves as a precursor for extracting device-level SEE cross-sections in ULP FPGAs using ISFD where conventional scrubbing or configuration readback interfaces (e.g., JTAG) are unavailable, enabling radiation characterization of highly resource-constrained devices.

Assessment of Objectives:

- System-level proton irradiation: Successfully located the potential hotspot of the system.
- Observation of proton-induced SEEs: Achieved
- Detection of destructive events: None observed
- ISFD functionality under radiation: Successfully demonstrated

Ongoing Analysis:

Further work includes statistical SEE analysis, energy-dependent event correlation, and detailed evaluation of memory bit-flip rates and RF performance degradation. These results will be reported in a subsequent publication and shared within the RADNEXT open data framework.

System-level proton irradiation of SpacePatch and ULP FPGAs successfully revealed non-destructive SEUs, with no latch-ups or permanent failures. The BLE SoC was the most radiation-sensitive subsystem, highlighting the need for innovative mechanisms to counteract SEUs in the SoC. The ISFD mechanism was validated, reliably detecting SEUs and showing potential for extracting SEE cross-sections in devices without standard scrubbing interfaces. These results demonstrate the feasibility of resilient, low-power electronics for deep-space wearable systems.

References:

[1] K. M. A. Rahman, T. Dirkes, B. Delfs, V. Wyrwoll and U. Kulau, "ISFD: Efficient and Fault-tolerant In-System-Failure-Detection for LP FPGA-based Smart-Sensors in Space Expeditions," 2024 20th International Conference on Distributed Computing in Smart Systems and the Internet of Things (DCOSS-IoT), Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, 2024, pp. 74-83, doi: 10.1109/DCOSS-IoT61029.2024.00021.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.